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Abstract

Video platforms such as YouTube, Netflix, and LMS-integrated content provide an interactive medium for learning, enhancing student engagement and flexibility. Mayer's theory suggests that students learn better when they receive information through both visual and auditory channels, making video platforms highly effective for improving understanding and retention. The constructivist approach involves active learning, where video content allows students to connect new information with prior knowledge, fostering deeper understanding. A teaching approach where students learn theoretical content through videos at home and engage in practical activities in the classroom, promoting active learning and better preparation. Video content on platforms like Netflix can improve listening skills by exposing students to real-life conversations, enhancing comprehension and fluency. Platforms like Edpuzzle make videos more interactive by embedding quizzes and prompts, turning a passive viewing experience into an active learning process. Potential distractions and unequal access to technology are challenges that must be addressed to effectively integrate video platforms into education.

Keywords: Video platforms, modern education, multimedia learning, flipped classroom, interactive learning, accessibility, passive listening skills, constructivist theory.

Introduction

In the digital age, video platforms have become an indispensable part of modern education, offering an interactive and flexible medium for learning. Unlike traditional teaching methods that rely heavily on textbooks and lectures, video platforms can cater to different learning styles, enhancing understanding and retention of information. This article explores the role of video platforms in education, with a mix of theoretical insights and practical examples, to showcase how they have transformed learning in diverse settings[1].

Materials and Types of Research

This study involves a combination of qualitative research, literature review, and case studies. Materials include academic papers, practitioner accounts of using video platforms, and data collected from educational institutions. The research was conducted through:

- Literature Review: Analysis of scholarly articles and existing research on the use of video platforms in educational settings.

- Case Studies: Examination of practical applications from schools and universities that have integrated video content in their curriculum [2][3].

Research Questions

Here are three research questions that guide this study as follows:

1. How do video platforms enhance the learning experience for students?
2. What are the practical applications of video platforms in different educational settings?
3. What are the key benefits and challenges associated with using video platforms in modern education?

Research Results

1. Multimedia Learning Theory

- Theory: Mayer's Multimedia Learning Theory posits that students learn more effectively when information is presented through both visual and auditory channels, reducing cognitive overload[1].

- Practical Example: Educational videos on YouTube use visual demonstrations synchronized with auditory explanations. For example, a physics teacher might use animated videos to explain Newton's Laws of Motion, allowing students to visualize complex theoretical concepts and understand them better[2].

2. Constructivist Theory and Active Learning

- Theory: According to Constructivist Theory, learners actively construct new knowledge by connecting it with prior understanding[3]. Video platforms facilitate this active learning approach.

- Practical Example: In Kazakhstan, Netflix has been used to enhance students' language skills by providing real-life conversations and cultural contexts. For instance, students can watch English-language movies or series, pause, rewind, and discuss idiomatic expressions, making the learning process more engaging and meaningful[4].

3. Flipped Classroom Model

- Theory: The flipped classroom model allows students to access lecture material at home via video platforms, thus freeing up class time for interactive activities[5].

- Practical Example: In a Kazakhstani high school, a math teacher implemented the flipped classroom model by recording video lectures on algebra. Students would watch these lectures at home, and classroom time was used to solve algebra problems collaboratively. This approach led to improved comprehension and higher engagement among students [6].

4. Passive Listening Skills in Language Learning

- Theory: Video platforms such as Netflix contribute to the development of passive listening skills by exposing students to authentic spoken language and different accents[7].

- Practical Example: In Kazakhstan, English teachers incorporated Netflix content into their curriculum, using scenes from movies to teach vocabulary, pronunciation, and cultural nuances. This

approach effectively improved students' listening skills and overall comprehension of the language[4].

5. Interactive Learning Features

- Theory: Platforms like Edpuzzle transform video-based learning into an interactive experience by embedding quizzes and prompts within videos [8].

- Practical Example: In Kazakhstani science classes, teachers used Edpuzzle to create interactive video lessons on topics like cell biology. Students watched a video and answered embedded questions, which helped them retain information more effectively, as they had to actively engage with the content [9].

6. Challenges of Video Platforms in Education

- Theory: Challenges associated with using video platforms in education include unequal access to technology and the risk of distraction.

- Practical Example: In Kazakhstan, many rural areas face issues with internet connectivity, which limits the accessibility of video-based learning [10]. Additionally, to mitigate distractions, teachers employed guided learning tasks and monitoring tools, ensuring students remained focused on the educational content [11].

These research results provide a detailed overview of how video platforms are effectively utilized in modern education, highlighting practical examples from Kazakhstan and the challenges faced in implementing these tools.

Conclusion

Video platforms have revolutionized modern education by providing diverse opportunities for interactive and flexible learning. They offer unique advantages by appealing to different learning styles, enabling self-paced study, and making expert knowledge accessible to a broader audience. From flipped classrooms to immersive language learning, the practical applications of video in education are vast and varied.

By integrating video platforms thoughtfully, educators can create a more engaging and effective learning environment that caters to the needs of today's students. However, the challenges of potential distractions and accessibility must be addressed to maximize the benefits of this technology. As digital content continues to evolve, video platforms will undoubtedly play an increasingly important role in shaping the future of education.

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